

The dependency of the Jordanian Public on the Jordanian TV and The Kingdom Channels as a Source of Information during the COVID 19 Pandemic

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
July 24, 2020

Accepted:
October 01, 2020

Keywords

Jordanian public,
Kingdom Channel,
Jordanian TV Channel,
Information, COVID 19

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4060392

Abstract

The study aimed at identifying the extent to which the Jordanian public depends on the Jordanian TV channel and the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis. The study used media dependency theory. The survey methodology was used on a random sample of the Jordanian public, which was (450) persons. According to the study findings, the majority of the study sample relied on the Kingdom channel as a main source of information during the Corona crisis, while a quarter of the study sample depended on the Jordanian TVchannel, as well as the main media content that the Jordanian public is keen to follow " News bulletins" in the Kingdom channel with an average of (2.79), followed by "press conferences and briefs" with an average of (2.72). Jordan's television news came in the first place (2.12), followed by "press conferences and briefs" with an average of (2.01).The results showed that there is a positive statistical relationship between the public's reliance on the Jordanian TV channel and the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis. And for the cognitive, emotional and behavioral implications of this dependence, results showed that the cognitive effects came at the top of the effects averaging (2.60), followed by the emotional effects with a small margin of an arithmetic average of (2.59). Finally, the behavioral effects are at the last with the average of (2.42), add to The Jordanian public has been shown to have statistically significant differences in the degree to which they depend on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (age group, educational level). On the other hand, the results have been shown to have no statistically significant differences according to gender and residence characteristics, the Jordanian public has been shown to have statistically significant differences in the degree to which they depend on the Jordanian TVchannel as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age group, residence, and educational level). Thus, by keeping in view the study findings, the researchers recommended more studies addressing the use of National media (radio, TV, social media) to spread Covid-19 awareness to mitigate the current healthcare crisis worldwide.

1. Introduction

Satellite news channels are among the most important and prominent of the indirect knowledge media for international issues and crises, and it is considered as an important source from which the public derives news and information. Satellite news channels are the key factor in the formation of public knowledge and a reference framework for the issues addressed through the huge numbers of news and information that increase daily. (Liu et al., 2020)The Corona crisis (COVID-19) - which devastated the world and violated borders has been six months since the world woke up to the news of this virus, as the world witnessed in this short period events that recall the periods of wars, and this new virus left its mark on all aspects of life; entire countries have been paralyzed, borders have been closed. Global economies slowed, schools closed, and social isolation left the streets empty. While the crisis in the world and the Middle East is devastating to many societies, economies and governments, a number of Arab countries are drowning in the face of protest movements to change their economic, social and political reality. The global attention to the news of the Corona crisis has increased, as the crisis is testing the media worldwide while these means seek to gain and maintain public confidence. The virus was not a scourge on the media, especially on television news. Since the crisis began, the number of its viewers has reached high levels that small screens have not known for decades, and they are widely popular for eager of information every day and those who are increasingly interested in the parallel levels of crisis development. The

news bulletins, talk shows and news analysis have high watching rates, reflecting the magnitude of the global ordeal we are experiencing today. And the need to keep the track of the news. (Al Jazeera, 2020). According to figures released by the British Broadcasting Corporation, the news bulletin at 6 p.m., which was shown on March 18, 2020 on the first television channel of the British corporation, has been watched by (9) million viewers, the highest number of viewers since Christmas in 2008. This is because of the pessimistic speech delivered by The British Prime Minister Boris Johnson, in which he called the British to be cautious during the crisis of Corona and to be ready to bid farewell to their loved ones, which attracted the viewers.(Al Jazeera, 2020)The role of the media is parallel to the governmental and security efforts in confronting this crisis, as the aftershocks of this crisis are still continuous until this study is conducted, and it is therefore incumbent on the media to convey the correct information to the public accurately and objectively, especially in time of crises. Information should be up to date to facilitate the necessary safety procedures without increasing public dismay.(Thurman et al., 2016). The power of the media lies on its control on the sources of information, by which the public depends to achieve its goals, (Aref El-Dabaa, 2007). It should be borne in mind that news television channels are sources on which the public relies to gain knowledge of the Corona crisis, especially after some countries decided to stop printing newspapers until further notice, including Jordan.

2. Study Problem and Questions

Media in the current era are more interested in the public because of the power of the influence on them, whether positive or negative, as the event is conveyed and interpreted, its content and content analysis are considered among the most important roles to be played, and the progress of Nations and peoples is measured by the flourishing of the media. (Downing, 1996)They are effective in times of crisis, making scientific research imperative. (Auverset &The media, in particular television - which combined sound and video- has been relied on by many audiences to achieve real information that directly affected their lives. The information they provided to the audience played an important role in informing them of what might happen in their social environment; especially with their interests in different age, educational and economic categories to follow up the crisis of Corona and its different effects. The crisis in Corona is new and there are no previous studies, so the current study seeks to cover this aspect. The Jordanian public is also trying to find out how much the Jordanian public depends on the Jordanian TVChannel and the Kingdom channel as a source of information during this crisis in light of media dependency theory. The problem of the study is therefore the following question: How much does the Jordanian public rely on the Jordanian TVand the Kingdom channels as a source of information during the Corona crisis? A set of sub-questions arises from this key question:

Q1: How far did the Jordanian public follow the Jordanian channels during the Corona crisis?

Q2: To what extent does the Jordanian public rely on the Jordanian TVand The Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis?

Q3: Why does the Jordanian public rely on the Jordanian TVChannel and the Kingdom Channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis?

Q4: What is the main media content of the Jordanian TVChannel and the Kingdom Channel that the Jordanian public is following during the Corona crisis?

Q5: What is the Jordanian public's assessment of the media treatment in the Kingdom's and The Jordanian TV channels of the Corona crisis?

Q6: What are the cognitive, emotional and behavioral effects of the public's reliance on the Kingdom's and The Jordanian TVchannels as a source of information during the Corona crisis?

3. Scientificof Study

The scarcity of scientific research and studies that dealt with the Jordanian public's reliance on Jordanian television channel and the Kingdomchannel as a source of information during the Corona crisis. As well as The study tackles an existing topic that continues to pose itself on the debate scene, which is the new Corona virus that has swept the whole world, and its effects may extend for a long time, add to The importance of identifying the sources of information on which the Jordanian public depends during the crisis, especially in light of the increasing effectiveness of Jordanian media in society, enriching scientific libraries with a recent study linking media with the Corona crisis, finally the Corona crisis directly affects the society, and therefore it deserves to be studied from media's perceptions and to be informed of the Jordanian public's opinion towards media coverage of the two channels the Jordanian TVchannel and the Kingdomchannel during the Corona crisis.

4. Literature Review

Many studies dealt with the subject of public dependence on different media as a source of information on a number of issues, and other studies dealt with crises, events and political and Arab issues, but there was no study dealing with the Jordanian public's dependence on the Jordanian TV channel and the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis. This is because the Corona crisis is a new subject that has not been studied and researched, so the researcher presented studies that deal with the public's dependence on the media as a source of information toward several issues and crises, and a number of Non-Arabic studies that dealt with the subject of Corona virus. Ayat Haider Hayadreh, (2019)conducted a study aimed at identifying the main differences in the main news bulletins in the Kingdom and the Jordanian TV channels, highlighted the topics on

which news bulletins focused in both channels, and concluded that the Kingdom and the Jordanian TV channels gave priority to economic topics. The results of the study showed that the two study channels depend on official sources in their news publications as the highest percentage in The Jordanian TV (92.5%), and for the Kingdom channel by (86.4%). Amin (2017) conducted a study that aims at revealing the extent to which the Bahraini public relies on the new media and its various applications to obtain information on sustainable development issues, and to monitor the cognitive and behavioral effects of exposure to such subjects on a sample of (250) individual Bahraini audiences. The findings found that most of the respondents felt that the new information provided limited information on sustainable development issues, because Arab media in general did not care much about such issues and demonstrated a lack of new information performance on awareness-raising and education on sustainable development issues. (Reda Abdel Wajid Amin, 2017). Similarly, Hussein, (2017) conducted a study that aims at identifying the extent of the Bahraini public's dependence on the different local media as a source of political information and to know the influence of these means in the Bahraini public on a sample of (407) persons. The study results concluded that the Internet comes at the top of the mass media for information, and showed that most of the sample feel the importance of the subjects and issues raised by Bahraini media, and also showed that more than two thirds of the sample trust Bahraini mass media. According to (Donia Waheed Atiq, 2016) tackled the Egyptian public's dependence on Arabic-speaking satellite channels and its trends toward the Arab political crisis frameworks in foreign satellite channels directed in Arabic as sources of information on those crises. The study aimed at monitoring and measuring the, on a sample of (400) person from the Egyptian public. The study concluded that there is a relation between the level of interest in the Arab political crises and depending on the news bulletins in the foreign satellite channels directed in Arabic to get information about those crises. The results of the study showed that there are statistically fair differences between the sample groups in terms of the average degree of direction toward the frameworks of dealing with the Arab political crises in foreign satellite channels. This is according to the changes of gender, age, education and party affiliation. Aref El-Dabaa, (2007) conducted a study aimed at identifying the extent to which the Egyptian public relies on the media to gain information about bird flu, and assessing the role that these methods play during crises, especially the bird flu crisis, on a sample of (700) persons from the Egyptian public. The results of the study found that television and newspapers came in the forefront of the mass media on which the sample members depend in the time of crises, and it is considered the preferred source for getting information about the crises that occur especially the news bulletins.

4.1 Non-Arabic studies

Buheji & Ahmed, (2020) conducted a study aimed at surveying the effects of social media on the spread of COVID-19 panic and its impact on mental health in the region of Iraqi Kurdistan, conducted on a sample of (516) social media users. The findings found that the social media were responsible for spreading the fear of COVID-19 among the people in Iraqi Kurdistan, and found that there was a great positive correlation between the social media and the spread of panic for COVID-19 with a significant value (0.8701). The types of the effects for panic on social media varies depending on gender, age and level of education, and according to the results of the study Facebook is the most widely used among social media means in spreading of fear of the COVID-19 outbreak in Iraq. As well the study of (Arif Al-Dabaa Refa'at., 2007) aimed at identifying the online search behavior associated with COVID-19 and the trends of "informational titles" (i.e. misinformation that leads to explanatory errors, false news, episodes of racism, etc.). Published in Italy using Google trends to explore COVID-19 Internet search from January to March 2020, the article titles have been extracted from the most read and e-government websites to investigate the situation of infectious titles spread across different regions and cities in Italy. According to the results of the study, key words such as "new coronary viruses", "Chinese coronary viruses", "COVID-19", "2019-COV" and "Sars-COV-2" are among the most important covid-19 terms common in Italy. The five most important health research operations were "facial masks", antiseptic, "symptoms of the new coronavirus", "healthy bulletin" and "coronavirus vaccines". The areas of (Umbria and Basilicata) recorded a large number of infectious titles, and the false information was widely disseminated in the Campania region. Similarly, study of (Xu et al., 2020) conducted a study aimed at examining and analyzing public attention to COVID-19 events in China at the beginning of the epidemic (December 31, 2019, February 20, 2020) through the Microblog hot list. According to the results of the study, the emotional trend of the public toward hot topics related to COVID-19 has changed from negative to neutral, with lack of negative emotions and increase of positive feelings as a whole, these topics were: The status and impact of new cases of COVID-19, forward reporting on the epidemic and prevention and control measures; Experts interpret discussed the source of infection, medical services in the front lines of the epidemic, focus on the global epidemic and look for suspicious cases, and also showed that social media (for example, Sina Microblog) can be used to measure public attention to public health emergencies during the new HIV epidemic. A large amount of information about the COVID epidemic has been disseminated.

Farooq et al., (2020) in their study which aimed to study the impact of online information on the individual's level's intention to voluntarily isolate themselves during the epidemic. According to the results of the study, Cyberchondria and the increased information have significantly affected individuals' threats and perceptions to

confront the epidemic, and through them the intention of self-isolation. The perceived intensity and self-competence ($P = 0.003$) have positively affected the intention of self-isolation, while the cost of response ($P.001$) has negatively affected intent, and Cyberchondria and the indirect overload of information have influenced the intention of self-isolation through the perceptions mentioned above. The use of social media has increased information and overanxiety among individuals, and no differences in perceptions have been found between people living alone and those living with their families.

5.1 Concepts of the Study

- **The Audience:** The number of people who have seen or been exposed to a television or radio program, measured by opinion and polling centers and bodies through Audiometer techniques, can also be relied upon opinions and samples (19). The Jordanian public, with its different categories, is both procedural and general.
- **Crisis:** it reflects the chaos and imbalance in the social system, as they point to chaos in countries, governments, and people, meaning more accurately the unstable situation that happens suddenly and breaks routine processes in each system. (20)
- **The Corona crisis:** A defect in the social system, chaos in all countries, governments and people, caused by the COVID-19 virus. A virus that has devastated the world, as there was no knowledge of the virus before the outbreak of the pandemic in the Chinese city of Johan in December 2010.
- **Information:** The data, semantics and knowledge that are related to the object or topic, and help those interested in identifying and knowing it. The information explains the concept of the object, and gives it a value, explains its characteristics, and shows its uses and functions. ()
- **The KingdomChannel:** A Jordanian news channel established under a special system on 10/7/2015, as the nucleus of an independent public information system. It seeks to provide a high-quality model as a public service channel offering comprehensive, round-the-clock coverage of events.(The official website ofthe KingdomChannel). And **Procedural:** It is an official Jordanian channel used as a tool of government public relations for information, direction and guidance.
- **The Jordanian TV channel** is an official public space channel opened by King Hussein Bin Talal on April 27, 1968, to serve the Jordanian public in all media fields. (Official the Jordanian TV website). The Jordanian government is using the government's media for guidance as a mean of media...

6. Theoretical Framework for Study

This study draws in part of its conceptual framework from media dependency theory, where it fits the subject of the study and achieves its objectives.The idea of this theory stems from the fact that with the complexity of life in modern societies and the continuous advancement in media technology, the importance of media has increased in the transmission of information. Individuals have tended to become more reliable in order to generate knowledge and attitudes toward what is happening in society and other societies. Relying on a choice or a preference for this individual is a result of satisfying the individual's specific personal or social needs.(Mahmoud Ismail, 1998).The basic idea of the theory of dependence can be summarized as having ability of the media to achieve greater influence will increase when media transfer information distinctly and intensively, and this possibility will increase in force if there is structural instability in society because of conflict and change (Mahmoud Ismail, 1998). Expressed in crisis, emergency or disaster situations, the media, the public and other social systems are mutually supportive.(Habes, 2019)Melvin Deviler, (1993), who developed this theory, believe that individuals rely on the media to achieve the following goals:

- understanding; through learning, gaining experience, and learning about the surroundings and their explanations.
- Guidance; includes self-direction such as making appropriate decisions, directing work and behavior such as deciding what to buy, and interactive guidance such as how to deal with new or challenging situations.
- Entertainment; it includes secluded entertainment such as rest and relaxation, social entertainment such as going for a movie, listening to music or watching TV with family or friends.

The main assumption of the accreditation theory is that the individual relies on the media to satisfy his needs through the use of the means, and the more the means plays an important role in the life of the individual, the greater its effect on him, and thus the relationship arises between the severity of dependence and the degree of the influence of the means among individuals, and the more complex societies become, the more individuals depend on media. (Baran & Davis, 2011)The theory is based on other sub-assumptions, according to Melvin Deviler, (1993) as following:

- The degree of stability of the social system affects the increase or lack of reliance on media information. In the case of social instability, the need for information increases and the reliance on the media increases.
- Media dependence is increased when there are few alternative channels of information, when there are multiple sources of information, individuals rely less on certain media.

- Individuals differ in the degree of dependence on the media due to their differences in individual goals, interests and needs.

The effects of dependence on the media are:

- a) Knowledge effects: It is related to removing ambiguities resulting from lack of information, forming trends towards community issues, prioritizing public attention, expanding its circle of beliefs, and clarifying the importance of values.
- b) Emotional effects: It is linked to emotional aspects such as fear and anxiety, alienation and emotional apathy.
- c) Behavioral Effects: It is that which activates the individual to perform a certain behavior as a result of a change in knowledge and conscience when exposed to the media. This is called activation, and the behavior may be inactivity and means inactivity, indifference, negativity and non-participating. (Ayat Haider Hayadreh, 2019).

The theory of media dependence is therefore one of the most appropriate media theories for this study, especially since it assumes that the Jordanian public is different in the degree of its dependence on the media. Because of its multiple sources of information, (Ngai et al., 2015) The degree of reliance of individuals on media information may be the basis for understanding the variables of the time and place of media messages and their impact on beliefs, feelings and behavior, and the funds of individuals vary on the media. (Song et al., 2004). This theory will be employed in the current study by identifying the following aspects:

- Identifying the degree to which the Jordanian public is relying on television as a source of information about the Corona crisis.
- Identifying why the public is using these resources to understand and guide them.
- Identifying the effects of reliance on these resources such as cognitive, emotional, and behavioral influences.

5.1. Study Hypotheses

H1: There is a statistically significant relationship between the public's dependence on the Jordanian TV channel the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis and the cognitive, emotional and behavioral implications of this reliance.

H2: There are statistical differences among the Jordanian public in the degree to which it relies on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis for their demographics (gender, age group, residence, and educational level).

H3: There are statistical differences among the Jordanian public in the degree to which it relies on The Jordanian TV as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age group, residence, and educational level).

6. Study Approach

Research Methodology is the central pillar of each study, as it is the path leading to uncovering the problem of the research and achieving its objectives. Besides, setting the general rule, of course, the methodology also includes the research plan, data collection tools, and previous studies that also used present methods. (Alghizzawi et al., 2018; Alhawamdeh et al., 2020; Rodríguez et al., 1996). The study is based on the e-questionnaire as a tool for collecting data and for answering study questions and hypotheses from the sample study, the study contains two parts: The first examines the characteristics of the sample population, such as gender, age group, educational level and residence. To achieve that the researcher chose a random sample of internet users by creating and downloading an electronic questionnaire through the Google site within the Google documents applications. (Farooq et al., 2020) The researcher published the link for the form by sending it via e-mail to lists of Internet users who reached (450) persons to be the study sample. The second examines the Jordanian public's dependence on the Jordanian TV channel and the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis. In addition, to publishing the questionnaire on a number of the social Facebook pages of the researcher, due to the difficulty of distributing it because of the exceptional circumstances of the country, and commitment to prohibiting touring. Table No. (1) shows the characteristics of the sample.

Table (1): the sample of the study

	Categories	Repetition	Percentage
Gender	Male	273	62.8
	Female	162	37.2
Age Group	From 20 years to less than 30 years	177	40.7
	From 30 years to less than 40 years	96	22.1

	From 40 years to less than 50 years	84	19.3
	50 years and above	78	17.9
Educational Level	High school or less diploma	51	11.7
	Bachelor	18	4.1
	MA and PhD	237	54.5
		129	29.7
Place of residence	City	261	60.0
	Village	144	33.1
	Desert	30	6.9

Total of the sample 435 for each variable and the percentage 100%

6.1 Validity and Stability

To measure the validity of the questionnaire, external truthfulness was tested by viewing the study to a group of academic and researchers in media who made some observations, and in light of their guidance the researcher made some adjustments to it, making the questionnaire valid for the final application. (Dikko, 2016) To ensure the stability of the instrument, the stability factor has been calculated in the internal consistency method according to the alpha-Cronbach equation of (0.89), and is considered appropriate for the purposes of this study.

6.2 Statistical Processing of Data

Data has been analyzed using a number of statistical methods, including:

- Frequencies, percentages, arithmetic averages, and standard deviations.
- Pearson's correlation coefficient of two variables.
- Analysis of the Anova, to examine statistical differences of more than two variables.
- Cronbach Alpha test for tool stability.

7. Data Analysis and Results:

below indicates the demographic data of study respondents. The data in table (2) shows that the majority of the study sample always follow the Kingdom channel at (57.9%), which is a high percentage, while (33.8%) of the research sample sometimes follow the Kingdom channel, and (8.3%) of the total study sample rarely follow The Kingdom channel (8.3%).

Table (2): Following up the Kingdom TV

Categories	Frequencies	percentage
Rarely	36	8.3%
Sometimes	147	33.8%
Always	252	57.9%
Total	435	100.0%

Table 3 data show that most of the study sample rarely follow the Jordanian TV with 53.8%, while 35.2% of the study sample sometimes follow Jordanian television. The percentage of those who follow the Jordanian TV always reached 11% of the total sample of the study.

Table 3: Following up the Jordanian TV

Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Rarely	234	53.8%
Sometimes	153	35.2%
Always	48	11.0%
Total	435	100.0%

Results show that the Jordanian public is following the Kingdom channel more than it is following The Jordanian TV channel, according to table 2 and table 3.

Table (4): The Kingdom channel as a source of information

Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Low	33	7.6%
Medium	63	14.5%
High	339	77.9%
Total	435	100.0%

Table (4) shows that the majority of the study sample depends on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis at a high rate of (77.9%), while (14.5%) of the sample depends on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis to a moderate degree. Whereas (7.6%) of

the study sample depends on the KingdomChannel as a source of information during the Corona crisis at a low rate.

Table (5): The Jordanian TV channel as a source of information

Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Low	189	43.4%
Medium	138	31.7%
High	108	24.8%
Total	435	100.0

Table (5) shows that the sample study depends on The Jordanian TV channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis at a high degree of reached (24.8%), which is a small percentage, while the rate of those who depend the Jordanian TV channel at a medium rate reached an average score of (31.7%). While the percentage of those who depend on it at a low rate reached (43.4%).

The two tables (4) and (5) confirm that the Jordanian public depends on The Kingdomchannel as a source of information during the Corona crisis at a high rate of (77.9%), while the Jordanian public dependence on the Jordanian TV channel reached (24.8%). This means that the Kingdomchannel was the most dependent of the Jordanian public, and this may be due to the possibilities that were provided to the Kingdomchannel as equipment's and human forces.

Table: (6) the favorite time for public to obtain information about Corona

Categories	Frequencies	Percentage
Morning	6	1.4%
Noon	21	4.8%
Evening	408	93.8%
Total	435	100.0

Table (6) shows that most of the study sample is keen to follow the Kingdom's and the Jordanian TVchannels for information about the Corona crisis in the evening at a high rate (93.8%), because the main news bulletins, press releases, and important talk shows are broadcast in the evening. Those who follow up in the morning were low, at (1.4%) of the total of the study sample, and (4.8%) of the total study sample followed up in the afternoon.

Table (7): Amount of hours for public in following up both channels

Categories	The Kingdom channel		The Jordanian TV channel	
	Frequencies	Percentage	Frequencies	Percentage
Low (less than 1 hour)	99	22.8%	336	77,2%
Medium (from 1 to 3 hours)	204	46.9%	75	17,2%
High (more than 3 hours)	132	30.3%	24	5,5%
Total	435	100.0%	435	100%

Table (7) data shows that the rate of follow-up by the Jordanian public for both the Kingdom channel and Jordan TV to obtain information about the Corona crisis at a high category (more than three hours) came in favor of the Kingdom channel at (30.3%) of the study sample, while its percentage in The Jordanian TV reached (5.5 %) of the study sample. An intermediate category (from one to three hours) came to the benefit of the Kingdom's channel also with (46.9%) of the study sample, and the percentage of this category in The Jordanian TV was (17.2%) of the study sample. As for a low category (less than an hour), it was in favor of Jordan TV with 77.2% of the study sample, and this percentage in the Kingdom channel reached 22.8% of the study sample.

1. Media contents that the Jordanian public is keen to follow on both the Kingdomand Jordanian TV channels about the Corona crisis.

To find outthis aspect, the repetitions, percentages, mean averages and standard deviations were extracted for the most important media contents that the Jordanian public is keen to follow in both the KingdomChannel and Jordan TV about the Corona crisis.

Table (8): Types of media content the public love to watch at Kingdom TV during Corona

Rank	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	SD	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	Newscasts	18	4.1	54	12.4	363	83.4	2.79	.497	High

2	Press conferences and briefs	30	6.9	60	13.8	345	79.3	2.72	.582	High
3	Talk shows	60	13.8	99	22.8	276	63.4	2.50	.726	High
4	Reporters' reports	69	15.9	132	30.3	234	53.8	2.38	.744	High

(More than one alternative can be selected)

Table (8) shows that the arithmetic averages ranged from (2.38-2.79) for the Kingdom channel's television spots. Paragraph (1) "News Bulletins" came in first place with an average of (2.79). The second was paragraph (4) "Press conferences and briefs" with an average (2.72), while "reporters' reports" in paragraph (3) was the last and with average account (2.38).

Table (9): Types of media content the public love to watch at Kingdom TV during Corona

Rank	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	SD	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	Newscasts	150	34.5	81	18.6	204	83.4	2.12	.895	Medium
2	Press conferences and briefs	159	36.6	111	25.5	165	79.3	2.01	.864	Medium
3	Talk shows	201	46.2	117	26.9	117	63.4	1.81	.834	Medium
4	Reporters' reports	222	51.0	135	31.0	78	53.8	1.67	.763	Medium

(More than one alternative can be selected)

Table 9 shows that the arithmetic averages ranged from (1.67-2.12) The Jordanian TV channel's spots, where paragraph (1) "news bulletins" ranked first and averaged (2.12), followed by paragraph 4 "press conferences and briefings" in the second place with an average of (2.01). Paragraph 2 "talk shows" came last and an average account (1.67).

Table (10): Reasons of depending on the Kingdom TV as source of information during Corona

Rank	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	SD	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	rapid transfer of events	27	6.2	45	10.3	363	83.4	2.77	.548	High
1	continuous follow-up of the developments of the Corona crisis	21	4.8	57	13.1	357	82.1	2.77	.522	High
2	interpreting and analyzing crisis events	18	4.1	81	18.6	336	77.2	2.73	.529	High
2	presenting the views of trusted jurisdictions	21	4.8	75	17.2	339	77.9	2.73	.542	High
3	Inclusion in the coverage of crisis events	24	5.5	84	19.3	327	75.2	2.70	.568	High
3	View the views of influential personalities in the crisis	21	4.8	87	20.0	327	75.2	2.70	.553	High
3	Provide awareness and health advice about the Corona crisis	21	4.8	90	20.7	324	74.5	2.70	.556	High
4	A mean I trust	27	6.2	90	20.7	318	73.1	2.67	.589	High
5	Accuracy in presenting data and information about the crisis	30	6.9	96	22.1	309	71.0	2.64	.607	Medium
6	Depth in crisis handling	36	8.3	141	32.4	258	59.3	2.51	.645	Medium

(More than one reason can be selected)

Table 10 shows that the arithmetic mean ranged from (2.51-2.77) for reasons of Jordanian public dependence on the Kingdom channel, with paragraphs (1 and 6) of the "rapid transfer of events" and "continuous follow-up of

the developments of the Corona crisis" in the first place with an average of (2.77). Second, paragraphs (2 and 7), "interpreting and analyzing crisis events", "presenting the views of trusted jurisdictions", and with an average of (2.73), followed by paragraph 3, "Depth in crisis handling", in the final place and with an average of (2.51).

Table (11):Table (10): Reasons of depending on the JRTV as source of information during Corona

No	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	SD	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	rapid transfer of events	129	29.7	174	40.0	132	30.3	2.01	.775	Medium
1	continuous follow-up of the developments of the Corona crisis	141	32.4	171	39.3	123	28.3	1.96	.779	Medium
2	interpreting and analyzing crisis events	150	34.5	159	36.6	126	29.0	1.94	.796	Medium
2	presenting the views of trusted jurisdictions	138	31.7	186	42.8	111	25.5	1.94	.755	Medium
3	Inclusion in the coverage of crisis events	144	33.1	180	41.4	111	25.5	1.92	.763	Medium
3	View the views of influential personalities in the crisis	138	31.7	198	45.5	99	22.8	1.91	.734	Medium
3	Provide awareness and health advice about the Corona crisis	159	36.6	177	40.7	99	22.8	1.86	.759	Medium
4	A mean I trust	180	41.4	153	35.2	102	23.4	1.82	.786	Medium
5	Accuracy in presenting data and information about the crisis	165	37.9	186	42.8	84	19.3	1.81	.734	Medium
6	Depth in crisis handling	36	39.3	141	32.4	87	20.0	1.81	.746	Medium

(More than one reason can be selected)

Table 11 shows that the arithmetic averages ranged from (1.81-2.01) for reasons of Jordanian public dependence on Jordanian television. As paragraph 10, "providing education and health guidance on the Corona crisis", was first ranked and averaged (2.01). Followed by paragraph (8), "A means I trust in", with an average of (1.96), followed by paragraphs (3 and 4), "Depth in dealing with the Crisis", and "coverage of crisis events", in the last place and with an average of 1.81.

Table (12):Arithmetic averages and standard deviations for the most important features of media coverage in the Kingdom channel of the Corona crisis

No	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	Standard deviation	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	pay special attention to the Corona crisis	114	26.2	186	42.8	135	31.0	2.05	.756	Medium
2	The use of specialists to address the dimensions of the Corona crisis	114	26.2	192	44.1	129	29.7	2.03	.747	Medium
3	Credibility and transparency	132	30.3	186	42.8	117	26.9	1.97	.757	Medium
4	View crisis topics at peak times	135	31.0	183	42.1	117	26.9	1.96	.761	Medium
5	Relying on talk shows in dealing with the crisis	144	33.1	186	42.8	105	24.1	1.91	.752	Medium
5	Not to be intimidated or downplayed from the Corona crisis	141	32.4	192	44.1	102	23.4	1.91	.743	Medium
6	The use of high in technologies	150	34.5	189	43.4	96	22.1	1.88	.743	Medium

	transporting events									
7	characterized by a bold coverage of the events of the crisis	159	36.6	174	40.0	102	23.4	1.87	.764	Medium
8	Balance of views	153	35.2	201	46.2	81	18.6	1.83	.715	Medium
8	Alert to the crisis before it occurs	165	37.9	180	41.4	90	20.7	1.83	.747	Medium

It is clear from Table No. (12) that the arithmetic averages ranged between (2.35-2.83) for the characteristics of media coverage in the Kingdom channel for the Corona crisis, and that the highest average is for "Paying special attention to the Corona crisis" which had an arithmetic average of (2.83), followed by a second aspect of "The use of specialists in dealing with the dimensions of the Corona crisis" with an average of (2.80), while the aspect of "Warning to the crisis before it occurred" came in the last rank and with an average of (2.35). It is also clear from the results of the table listed above that the Jordanian public believes that the Kingdom channel "pay special attention to the Corona crisis", and that this general characteristic came in a high degree. This result explains that the Kingdom channel succeeded in covering the Corona crisis and getting close to the public by highlighting what public cares about and what public needs to know.

Table (13): Media coverage in the Jordan TV channel of the Corona crisis

No	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	SD	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	rapid transfer of events	9	2.1	57	13.1	369	84.8	2.83	.430	High
2	continuous follow-up of the developments of the Corona crisis	9	2.1	69	15.9	357	82.1	2.80	.449	High
3	interpreting and analyzing crisis events	9	2.1	84	19.3	342	78.6	2.77	.471	High
4	presenting the views of trusted jurisdictions	27	6.2	69	15.9	339	77.9	2.72	.572	High
5	Inclusion in the coverage of crisis events	21	4.8	87	20.0	327	75.2	2.70	.553	High
6	View the views of influential personalities in the crisis	12	2.8	120	27.6	303	69.7	2.67	.527	High
6	Provide awareness and health advice about the Corona crisis	21	4.8	102	23.4	312	71.7	2.67	.565	High
7	A mean I trust	24	5.5	111	25.5	300	69.0	2.63	.586	High
8	Accuracy in presenting data and information about the crisis	27	6.2	117	26.9	291	66.9	2.61	.603	High
9	Depth in crisis handling	54	12.4	174	40.0	207	47.6	2.35	.691	High

It is clear from Table (13) that the arithmetic averages ranged between (1.83-2.05) for the characteristics of media coverage on Jordan TV for the Corona crisis, and that the highest average for "credibility and transparency" with an average arithmetic average of (2.05), followed by the "the use of specialists in dealing with the dimensions of the Corona crisis" with an average score of (2.03), while the aspect of " alerting to the crisis before it occurred "and" using high technologies in reporting events "came in the last rank with an average of (1.83).It is also clear from the results of the table listed above that the Jordanian public believes that The Jordanian TV is credible and transparent, and that the general characteristics came with a moderate degree. This result explains that The Jordanian TV needs more work to increase the public's confidence in it, and that it strives to use high technologies in transferring the events.

Table (14): The effects of the Jordanian public's dependence on both the Kingdom and JRTV

no	Paragraphs	Never		To some extent		To high extent		Arithmetic Ave.	SD	degree
		N	%	N	%	N	%			
1	I have more respect for the men of the Jordanian armed forces, security services and medical personnel	9	2.1	66	15.2	360	82.8	2.81	.445	High

2	Awareness of the seriousness of this virus and what it can cause	12	2.8	99	22.8	324	74.5	2.72	.509	High
3	The small number of injuries in the recent period made me feel comfortable and relax	12	2.8	105	24.1	318	73.1	2.70	.514	High
3	Committed to stay at home and leave only when necessary, subject to general safety rules	15	3.4	99	22.8	321	73.8	2.70	.527	High
4	These means have demonstrated the importance of compliance with the instructions	15	3.4	111	25.5	309	71.0	2.68	.537	High
5	These means explained how the virus spread, and why it spread	30	6.9	105	24.1	300	69.0	2.62	.612	High
6	It has contributed to my introduction to many figures that I did not know about before the crisis	21	4.8	126	29.0	288	66.2	2.61	.578	High
7	Sympathize with the families of those infected with the virus.	30	6.9	120	27.6	285	65.5	2.59	.618	High
8	It has contributed to my information about the Corona virus through the informative messages	30	6.9	129	29.7	276	63.4	2.57	.620	High
9	Explained the most important effects of the Corona crisis in all areas.	33	7.6	135	31.0	267	61.4	2.54	.633	High
10	Following the Corona crisis in these channels made me worried about the Jordanian economy	45	10.3	129	29.7	261	60.0	2.50	.677	High
11	Following these channels reduce the risk of Corona virus	63	14.5	114	26.2	258	59.3	2.45	.734	High
12	I participated in Discussions and dialogues on the Corona crisis depending on what you I in these channels	120	27.6	129	29.7	186	42.8	2.15	.826	medium
13	I donated money in support of national efforts and mitigated the damage of this crisis	156	35.9	105	24.1	174	40.0	2.04	.871	medium

The results of table (14) show that all the effects of the Corona crisis came in an average of (2.54), with the cognitive effects at the top of the effects on an average of (2.60), followed by the emotional effects with a small margin at an average of (2.59), and finally the behavioral effects came at the last average of (2.42).

The following are the effects in details:

• **Cognitive effects**

The first expression on the cognitive effects was "these methods have shown the importance of adhering to the instructions, and ensuring that they are implemented" by an average of (2.68), followed by " showing how the virus spreads, and why it spreads at an average of (2.62), followed by other expressions of cognitive effects, as follows:

- It contributed to the introduction of many characters, I did not know about before the crisis, with an average of (2.61)
- It has contributed to my information about the Corona virus through an average 2.57 awareness messages
- The most significant effects of the Corona crisis in all areas were explained by an average of (2.54)

The previous results indicate that the arithmetic mean of the expressions of measuring the cognitive influence of the Jordanian public's dependence on both the Kingdom and the Jordanian television channels as a source of information about the Corona crisis has increased, which indicates the cognitive influence of these means and providing them with news and information about the crisis to the public. It also indicates that reliance on information in certain circumstances contributes to an individual's knowledge of the information and events

associated with those circumstances, which supports the basic assumptions of the study theory. (Al-Lahham, 2016).

- **Emotional effects:**

"Awareness of the seriousness of this virus and what it can cause" came in the forefront of the expressions about the emotional effects, which indicate the emotional impact of the media. The other expressions on the emotional effects were as follows:

- The low number of injuries in the recent period made me feel comfortable and comfortable with an average of (2.70)
- I sympathize with the families of people infected with the virus. My parents who died on an of average (2.59)
- Following the Corona crisis in these channels, I was worried about the Jordanian economy at an arithmetic with an average of (2.50)
- Following these channels reduce the risk of the Corona virus by an average of (2.45)

The results indicate that the arithmetic averages of the expressions of measuring the emotional impact of the approval of the Jordanian public are high. The Kingdom and the Jordanian television channels should each provide information source on the crisis of Corona, where the five terms came to a high degree, which indicates that the dependence on these channels has led to positive emotional effects. This is consistent with the theory of media dependence that during times of change, ambiguity, or crisis, dependence on them removes ambiguity, lessening or increasing tension.

- **Behavioral effects:**

The phrase "I respect more the men of the Jordanian Armed forces, the security services and medical personnel" was the first expression of the behavioral effects on an average of (2.81). This refers to the important role of these channels in clarifying the work of these bodies, the burden they have on themselves and providing the individual with the information that enabled them to create a correct image.

The second arrangement was the phrase "committed to stay at home and not to leave except when necessary, taking into account the general safety rules" with an average of (2.70). These results also indicate the positive role of these channels in influencing the Jordanian public and forcing them not to leave homes.

The phrase "I participated in discussions and dialogues on Corona crisis based on what I saw from these channels" came in a mean of (2.15). This result indicates that these channels provided the public with the information that enabled them to hold dialogues and discussions on the Corona crisis with others. The phrase "I donated money in support of national efforts and mitigated the damage of this crisis" reported also that the government has been working with the government to improve the situation in the country.

7.1 Study hypotheses results

- **H1:** There is a statistically significant relationship between the public's dependence on the Jordanian television and Kingdom channels as a source of information during the Corona crisis and the cognitive, emotional and behavioral implications of this dependence.

Table (15): The correlation coefficient between public dependence on JRTV and Kingdom TV

H1		Cognitive effects	Emotional effects	Behavioral effects
How reliable are you on the Kingdom Channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis?	Correlation coefficient r	.458 (**)	.382	.305 (**)
	Statistical significance	.000	.000	.000
	Number	435	435	435
How reliable are you on Jordanian television as a source of information during the Corona crisis?	Correlation coefficient r	*.104	.204(**)	311(**)
	Statistical significance	.030	.000	.000
	Number	435	435	435

- statistical function at the significance level (0.05).

Table 15 shows a statistically positive relationship between the public's dependence on the Jordanian television and Kingdom channels as a source of information during the Corona crisis and the cognitive, emotional, and behavioral implications of this dependence, which confirms the validity of the first hypothesis.

- **H2:** There are statistically significant differences among the Jordanian public in the degree to which it depends on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age group, residence, And the level of education).

To test this hypothesis, the arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the degree to which the Jordanian audience relies on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis, according to the gender, age group, residence, and educational level variables, and to indicate the statistical differences between the arithmetic mean the variance analysis was used, and the table below shows this.

Table (16): the correlation between depending on both channels and demographic variables

	Categories	Arithmetic Ave.	SD	P	df	Sig.
Gender	Male	2.68	.610	.296	433,1	.586
	Female	2.74	.585			
Age Group	From 20 years to less than 30 years	2.80	.515	4.485	431,3	.004
	From 30 years to less than 40 years	2.75	.503			
	From 40 years to less than 50 years	2.50	.784			
	50 years and above	2.65	.621			
Educational Level	High school or less	2.88	.475	4.716	431,3	.003
	Diploma	2.83	.383			
	Bachelor	2.73	.568			
	MA and PhD	2.56	.695			
Place of residence	City	2.69	.614	.291	432,2	.748
	Village	2.73	.570			
	Desert	2.70	.651			

Table 16 shows the following:

- There are no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) that are attributable to the genre.
- There are statistically significant differences (including the $\alpha = 0.05$) due to the effect of the age group. To illustrate statistically significant even differences between arithmetic averages, the following comparisons were used in the LSD method as shown in Table No. 17.
- There are statistically significant differences (including $\alpha = 0.05$) due to the effect of the educational level. To illustrate statistically significant even differences between arithmetic averages, the following comparisons were used in the LSD method as shown in Table No. 18.
- There are no statistically significant differences ($\alpha = 0.05$) due to the effect of the residence.

Table (17): Post comparison by LSD method for age-group impact

Age group	Arithmetic Ave.	From 20 years to less than 30 years	From 30 years to less than 40 years	From 40 years to less than 50 years	50 years and above
From 20 years to less than 30 years	2.80				
From 30 years to less than 40 years	2.75	.05			
From 40 years to less than 50 years	2.50	.30*	.25*		
50 years and above	2.65	.14	.10	-.15	

* function at significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$).

Table 17 shows differences of statistical significance (including: $\alpha = 0.05$) between 40 years and under 50 years on one hand, and 20 years for less than 30 years, and 30 years for less than 40 years on the other. The differences were in favor of each of 20 years under 30 and 30 years under 40.

Table (18): LSD post comparisons of the effect of the educational level

Educational Level	Arithmetic Ave.	High school or less	diploma	Bachelor	MA and PhD
High school or less	2.88				
diploma	2.83	.05			
Bachelor	2.73	.15	.10		
MA and PhD	2.56	.32*	.28	.18*	

* function at significance level ($\alpha= 0.05$).

Table 18 shows differences of statistical significance (including: $\alpha= 0.05$) between a master's degree and PH. D degree on the one hand, and a minor's secondary school, and a bachelor's degree on the other hand. The differences were in favor of both a lower general secondary school or less and a bachelor's degree. **The second hypothesis clear:** There are statistically significant differences among the Jordanian public in the degree to which it is based on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (age group and the level of education). The absence of statistical disparities among the Jordanian public in the degree to which they are based on the Kingdom's channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, place of residence).

H3: There are statistically significant differences among the Jordanian public in the degree to which they are based on Jordanian television as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age group, residence, and other aspects of the situation. And the level of education). To verify this hypothesis, the arithmetic mean and standard deviations of the Jordanian audience's dependence on Jordan's TV channel was extracted as a source of information during the Corona crisis, according to the gender, age group, residence, and educational level variables, and to indicate the statistical differences between the mean calculations the variance analysis was used, and the table below shows this.

Table (19): Public depending on JRTV according to demographic variables.

	Categories	Arithmetic Ave.	Standard deviation	P	df	Sig.
Gender	Male	1.71	.790	8.618	433,1	.004
	Female	1.98	.807			
Age Group	From 20 years to less than 30 years	1.88	.827	3.070	431,3	.028
	From 30 years to less than 40 years	1.69	.772			
	From 40 years to less than 50 years	1.93	.803			
	50 years and above	1.69	.778			
Educational Level	High school or less	1.82	.865	2.979	431,3	.031
	Diploma	1.83	.707			
	Bachelor	1.92	.825			
	MA and PhD	1.60	.723			
Place of residence	City	1.66	.742	13.055	432,2	.000
	Village	2.10	.800			
	Desert	1.80	.997			

Table 19 shows the following:

The difference between the two genders, and the difference is in favor of the females.

- There are statistically significant differences (including the ($\alpha =0.05$) due to the effect of the age group. To illustrate statistically significant even differences between arithmetic averages, the following comparisons were used in the LSD method as shown in Table 20.
- There are statistically significant differences ($\alpha =0.05$) due to the effect of the educational level. To illustrate statistically significant even differences between arithmetic averages, the following comparisons were used in the LSD method as shown in Table No. 21.
- There are statistically significant differences ($\alpha =0.05$) due to the effect of the residence. To illustrate statistically significant even differences between arithmetic averages, the following comparisons were used in the LSD method as shown in Table 22.

Table (20): LSD for age-group impact

Age group	Arithmetic Ave.	From 20 years to less than 30 years	From 30 years to less than 40 years	From 40 years to less than 50 years	50 years and above
From 20 years to less than 30 years	1.88				
From 30 years to less than 40 years	1.69	.19*			
From 40 years to less than 50 years	1.93	.05	.24*		
50 years and above	1.69	.19	.00	.24*	

* function at significance level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table 20 shows differences of statistical significance (including: ($\alpha=0.05$) between 30 years and under 40 years on one hand, and 20 years for under 30 years, and 40 years for under 50 years on the other hand. The differences were in favor of each of 20 years under 30 years, 40 years under 50 years, and statistically significant differences (including the $\alpha=0.05$) between 50 years and over and 40 years under 50 years of age were found, and the differences were in favor of 40 years under 50 years.

Table (21): LSD_ method post comparisons for educational level impact

Educational Level	Arithmetic Ave.	High school or less	diploma	Bachelor	MA and PhD
High school or less	1.82				
diploma	1.83	.01			
Bachelor	1.92	.10	.09		
MA and PhD	1.60	.22	.23	.32*	

* function at significance level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table 21 shows differences of statistical significance (including: ($\alpha=0.05$) between the two degrees (M.Sc., Ph.D.), and the Bachelor's degree.

Table (22): LSD-style post comparisons of the impact of the residence

Place of residence	Arithmetic Ave.	City	Village	Badia
City	1.66			
Village	2.10	.45*		
Desert	1.80	.14	.30*	

Function at function level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table 22 shows that there are statistically significant differences (including the ($\alpha=0.05$) between a village on one hand, and a city and the desert on the other and the differences are in favor of the village. The validity of the third hypothesis is as follows: There are statistically significant differences among the Jordanian public in the degree to which they are depend on Jordanian television as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age group, residence, and educational level).

8. Conclusion and future research:

The study aimed at identifying the extent to which the Jordanian public depends on the Jordanian television and Kingdom channels as a source of information during the Corona crisis, and the researcher has reached the most prominent results, which are as follows: The results showed that the majority of the sample study depends on the Kingdom channel as a source of information during the Corona crisis. While quarter of the study sample depended on Jordanian television as a source of information during Corona crisis. The results showed that the most important media content that the Jordanian public is keen to follow in the first place "News broadcasts" on the Kingdom channel during the crisis of Corona, followed by "press conferences and briefings" in the second place. Jordanian television reported the news "first place", followed by "press conferences and briefings". As well as the findings show that the cognitive effects are at the forefront of the effects, followed by emotional effects. Finally, the behavioral effects came. The positive statistically significant relationship between the public's dependence on the Jordanian television and Kingdom channels as a source of information during the Corona crisis and the cognitive, emotional and behavioral implications of this dependence has been demonstrated. The extent to which the Jordanian public is depending on the Kingdom channel as a source of information is shown to be statistically fair differences during the Corona crisis, according to their demographics (age group, educational level), and the absence of significant differences according to characteristics (gender, place of residence). The Jordanian public has been shown to have statistically significant differences in the degree to which it is depend on Jordanian television as a source of information during the Corona crisis according to their demographic characteristics (gender, age group, residence, and educational level).

Results explicitly revealed that a majority of the individuals agreed on the importance of The dependency of the Jordanian Public on the Jordanian TV and The Kingdom Channels as a Source of Information during the COVID 19 pandemic. Thus, the researcher hopes To activate Jordanian television's role in covering local events, especially during crises in non-traditional ways, to keep up with competition requirements professionally and financially and to boost financial revenues and Preparing studies to address the reasons for the low dependence on Jordanian television as a source of information, and developing it as a means of official media; to make it more effective and reliable for the Jordanian public as an important source of information. as well as to conduct periodic studies that measure the viewer's satisfaction with the programs being displayed, it is used to improve the format and content of programs that are generally preferred by the Jordanian public. add to Develop national information strategies that allow for the production of targeted and successful media content, especially in times of crisis, finally support Jordanian television in order to compete with other channels and to work on developing the performance of its employees with media training. It is the first national visual media medium.

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